

STUDY ON THE OPTIMIZATION PATH OF ACADEMIC EARLY WARNING MECHANISM

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ABSTRACT

The academic early warning mechanism is an important measure for improving the quality of talent cultivation in local universities. However, the current mechanism is lacking in flexibility, systematicity, and synergy, which reduces its effectiveness and relevance. This paper examines the problems of the current academic early warning mechanism at a local university using a combination of literature review and descriptive research. Under the background of "Three All-round Education", focused optimization suggestions are offered, and an 'academic early warning mechanism for college students' is built with subject synergy, cycle development, and three-dimensional support. The study suggests optimization strategies based on the concept of "Three All-round Education". It also develops an academic early warning system for college students that includes 'subject synergy,' 'cycle development,' and 'three-dimensional support.' The study found that by strengthening the synergistic efficacy of the main body of education, basing it on the whole cycle of academic development, and strengthening the three-dimensional support system, an all-member, all-process, all-around academic early warning mechanism can be effectively constructed, which will help colleges to strengthen the construction of academic atmosphere. This mechanism can assist colleges in strengthening the foundation of academic culture and improving the quality of talent development. This study applies the concept of "Three All-round Education" to explore the optimization path of college students' academic early warning mechanisms. The study enriches the theory of education management and provides important theoretical contributions and practical guidance for improving the college academic management system and optimizing teaching quality.

Keywords: Optimization strategies, academic early warning, three all-round educations, operational efficiency, academic committee

INTRODUCTION

The Ministry of Education of China published "Opinions on Deepening Undergraduate Education and Teaching Reform and Comprehensively Improving Talent Training Quality" in 2019 (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2019; Opinions of the Ministry of Education on Deepening the Reform of Undergraduate Education and Teaching and Comprehensively Improving the Quality of Talent Training), and highlights the significance of strong control over

examinations and graduation criteria, as well as the complete cancellation of exam clearing. These new criteria require colleges and universities to boost their academic style. Academic early warning is a critical step toward establishing a good academic style in universities. It is based on the development and execution of a scientific early warning mechanism to precisely identify academic dangers, increase students' self-management skills, and mold a positive academic style (Xiong, 2023). Academic early warning is an important technique for monitoring undergraduates' academic progress at universities. Its importance is in boosting the quality of talent development, optimizing the teaching management system, and cultivating a rigorous and pragmatic academic style. To help students facing academic challenges make significant progress, colleges, and universities should concentrate on developing self-management skills, promoting peer-assisted learning, strengthening mechanisms for constructing academic styles, improving education and teaching management systems, and optimizing academic early warning and assistance mechanisms (Yang et al., 2023). When developing mechanisms, colleges should place a high priority on advancing moral education while simultaneously fortifying the notion of an education that is "student-oriented." One crucial step in enhancing academic culture and advancing students' academic achievement is the implementation of an academic early warning system (Xu et al., 2023). The idea of "Three All-round Education" is vital to modern higher education. It includes whole-staff, whole-process, and all-around parenting and places a strong emphasis on the continuance of the educational process, the integration of educational resources, and the holistic development of pupils (Zuo & Lai, 2023). The installation of an academic early warning mechanism for college students is critical for increasing the quality of talent development, optimizing the teaching management system, and cultivating a good academic style. This article examines the limitations of the current academic early warning system at local colleges and universities. It integrates the meaning and requirements of the concept of "Three All-round Education" and gives actionable optimization strategies. The goal is to provide valuable references for colleges and universities to help them build an academic culture and improve talent development.

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

This study systematically collects, organizes, and analyzes the literature and documents on academic early warning, examines the shortcomings of the current academic early warning mechanism in a local college, and explores the means of optimization based on the "three all-around education." By optimizing the academic early warning mechanism, colleges can accurately identify students with academic problems, provide timely and effective support and intervention to help them overcome academic challenges, and improve their academic performance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study mainly analyzes the problems and shortcomings of the existing academic early warning mechanism of local universities and tries to explore the optimization of the academic early warning mechanism of universities under the concept of "Three All-round Education", so as to improve the implementation effect of academic early warning. Therefore, this study will mainly focus on the following two research questions:

RQ1. What are the deficiencies and shortcomings of the current academic warning mechanism in local universities?

RQ2. How can we improve the academic early warning mechanism in universities to address these concerns and shortcomings?

LITERATURE REVIEW

ACADEMIC EARLY WARNING

Academic early warning refers to the school's frequent data on students' semester learning, according to student management standards and talent development programs. It involves informing students and their parents about the potential negative impact of existing learning problems and challenges (Xu et al., 2023). An institutional information and crisis warning mechanism that alerts students to their academic development trends through multi-party cooperation among schools, society, parents, and students by providing timely reminders or advance notice of potential difficulties and problems in students' learning (Liu et al., 2023). Constructing a process-oriented academic early warning mechanism and a diversified support system centered on students can significantly improve the quality of talent cultivation. However, the use of digital tools, such as artificial intelligence, should be enhanced to build predictive models that identify students with low-grade point averages (GPAs) at graduation and help them improve their academic performance (Ajrina et al., 2023). An academic early warning and help service framework is constructed using big data student portrait technology. The K-means algorithm is combined to establish an intelligent academic early warning model. This model provides powerful support for the digital evaluation and accurate early warning of college students' academics. To address the diverse and unique academic problems of students, personalized and precise help measures are necessary. This requires the in-depth involvement of professional teachers and counselors to ensure the effective integration of online education and offline management, comprehensively meeting students' academic needs (Xiong, 2023). Constructing a mechanism of 'warning-alert-help' throughout the undergraduate academic education process, with vertical and horizontal linkage, full participation, and multi-party force, can facilitate positive interaction between academic warning, alert, and help and effectively improve the academic performance of undergraduates. The mechanism can facilitate positive interaction between academic warning, alert, and help, effectively improving the support provided to students facing academic difficulties. However, it is crucial to maintain the mechanism's flexibility and adaptability during its operation and make timely adjustments in response to changes in college students' psychological, emotional, and employment issues (Li et al., 2023).

THREE ALL-ROUND EDUCATIONS

The concept of "Three All-round Education" emphasizes students' active participation and comprehensive development and highlights their subjective position. This approach can effectively address the shortcomings of traditional education, such as poor communication and stereotypical teaching. It can also stimulate students' interest and potential in learning, resulting in significant improvements in their academic performance (Lu & Lu, 2021). Guided by the concept of "Three All-round Education", we promote the construction of an academic style that adheres

to the principles of student-centeredness, citation integration, and management. We also promote mutual learning and teaching through 'multi-party linkage'. Based on the characteristics of the profession, we aim to cultivate students' learning behaviors and habits by promoting the 'three-classroom linkage'. By regulating students' negative habits, promoting the 'three halls linkage', and creating a learning community, we can cultivate students' learning behavior and enhance the effectiveness of education (Zhang & Cheng, 2023). According to Chen and Zou (2022), an all-staff support system can be constructed based on the concept of "Three All-round Education", from professional teachers to students' backbones and combined with a continuous support system for the whole process, including prevention before, intervention during, and tracking after the process, to realize accurate support for students with academic difficulties. By integrating the concept of "Three All-round Education" and providing educational support for students with academic difficulties, we can effectively combine the resources of schools, families, and society. This will help establish a multi-party and multi-layer management intervention and support system for students with academic difficulties, focusing on academic improvement, internalization of moral education, and social integration. The ultimate goal is to assist students with academic difficulties in their growth and success (Dong et al., 2020).

METHODOLOGY

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The concept and goal of education known as "Three All-round Education" emphasize the comprehensive development of students' personalities. It focuses on improving students' knowledge accumulation, ability cultivation, character shaping, emotional intelligence, and aesthetics. This approach promotes the overall improvement of students' self-development and social adaptability (Zuo & Lai, 2023). This provides comprehensive guidance for optimizing the academic early warning mechanism. To ensure comprehensive parenting, the academic early warning mechanism should involve all educators, including teachers, counselors, and parents. This will create an educational synergy and enable them to monitor students' academic development. To ensure continuous attention to and timely intervention in students' academic situations, the academic early warning mechanism should be implemented throughout the entire learning process, from enrollment to graduation (Li et al., 2023). In regard to comprehensive parenting, the academic early warning mechanism should pay attention to various aspects of students' academics, psychology, and life to promote their overall development. Therefore, this study is based on the concept of "Three All-round Education", which can achieve all-inclusive, all-encompassing, and all-around academic early warning in order to establish a comprehensive, systematic, and synergistic academic early warning mechanism for college students.

RESEARCH DESIGN

To optimize the academic early warning mechanism for college students in local undergraduate colleges and universities in western China, this study first examines research on the construction of academic early warning mechanisms and the optimization of paths in 'CNKI' and 'CQVIP' through literature and descriptive research methods. Then, it analyzes documents and notices on the official websites of major colleges and universities. After consulting a large number of documents and notices on academic early warning from major university websites, the deficiencies of the current academic early warning mechanism for college students were identified in order to determine the research problem. We utilized the exploratory research method to develop a new academic early warning mechanism that meets practical needs and effectively improves implementation by combining the concept of "Three All-round Education" with the author's management experience. Subsequently, we conducted a search for studies on optimizing academic early warning mechanisms on Google Scholar. The author plans to conduct a qualitative study in their subsequent research to verify the rationality of the designed program evaluation model. Fifty students experiencing academic difficulties at a local undergraduate university in western China were selected as research subjects for a six-month educational management study. The study aimed to explore their perceptions, experiences, and suggestions on the new academic early warning mechanism through semi-structured interviews. The collected data were thematically analyzed, coded, and interpreted.

FINDINGS

This study examines the inflexibility, lack of systematization, and lack of coordination in the academic early warning system for college students in local colleges and universities. It proposes a new mechanism called the 'synergy of subjects—cycle development—three-dimensional support' based on the concept of "Three All-round Education". The proposed academic early warning mechanism for college students is based on the concept of "Three All-round Education". The academic early warning and support mechanism has been strengthened by enhancing the synergy of the educational body and involving all staff. This ensures maximum utilization of educational resources and the formation of educational synergy. The academic early warning system has been perfected by focusing on the entire academic development cycle of students and implementing a continuous monitoring process. This ensures timely intervention in the academic situation of students. The three-dimensional support system has been strengthened, and the all-around academic early warning mechanism has been deepened to provide more comprehensive and personalized support to students.

DISCUSSION

TO ENHANCE THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION AND ESTABLISH A MECHANISM FOR FULL PARTICIPATION IN ACADEMIC EARLY WARNING

The implementation of the academic early warning mechanism should not solely rely on the strength of counselors or teaching offices. Instead, it should build a diversified and synergistic education and guidance system that utilizes the roles of professional teachers, peer tutors, parents, psychological counselors, and other parties in education and guidance. This approach can ensure better results for academic early warning and support work. Counselors have a coordinating role in the academic early warning mechanism. They possess an in-depth understanding of and trust in students, which enables them to carefully grasp students' family backgrounds, learning situations, and behavioral performance. Counselors communicate with students through personalized support measures to promote their academic progress. At the same time, the dynamic linkage between counselors, teaching offices, professional teachers, and parents helps to grasp the students' academic status in real-time and then implement accurate and effective intervention and support. The teaching office plays a crucial role in academic guidance through the academic early warning mechanism. It is responsible for interpreting and answering questions related to the talent cultivation program, academic management, and other related systems. Additionally, it helps students clarify their learning goals and paths. When students receive an academic warning, the teaching office should promptly inform them of their current situation and provide guidance on how to improve their academic performance. This may include suggestions such as making up missed exams and additional studying. Early warning education should also be provided to students to help them understand the potential consequences of their academic status. Effective communication between the teaching office and counselors is crucial to ensuring standardized and timely academic interventions. Course instructors play a professional guidance role in the academic early warning mechanism, and with their own professional knowledge and experience, they can provide targeted Q&A services for students with academic difficulties. At the same time, teachers provide feedback on students' classroom performance and learning status to counselors and the teaching office. This helps all parties to have a more comprehensive understanding of students' learning situations and formulate more effective support measures. Peer tutors play a crucial role in the academic early warning mechanism by promoting behavior and habit formation. They assist students with academic difficulties in developing good study habits and improving their independent learning abilities through one-on-one pairing and sharing of learning experiences. The importance of parental involvement in education and guidance cannot be overstated. Parents should actively cooperate with schools to carry out ideological guidance work, encourage students to overcome learning difficulties, and enhance their self-confidence in learning. Psychological counselors play a crucial role in providing professional psychological counseling and tutoring services to help students relieve learning pressure and prevent the occurrence of psychological crises in the academic early warning mechanism. By building a diversified and synergistic education and guidance system, all parties involved in education and guidance can better support academic early warning work.

TO IMPROVE THE ACADEMIC EARLY WARNING MECHANISM BASED ON THE ENTIRE CYCLE OF THE ACADEMIC EARLY WARNING MECHANISM

To enhance the academic early warning mechanism, we have implemented the 'six concerns' that consider the entire cycle of students' academic development. The starting point of academic development is enrollment information. Counselors and academic advisors should analyze students' basic information, including their college entrance examination scores and family backgrounds, to identify potential academic risks, such as those who may be disadvantaged due to bias, ethnicity, or coming from educationally disadvantaged areas. Targeted support measures should be implemented in advance. To monitor students' learning progress in real-time, it is important to focus on their daily performance. Through joint observation by counselors, teachers, and peer tutors, we monitor students' classroom attendance, homework completion, psychological status, and other performance indicators to identify learning difficulties and intervene in a timely manner. To evaluate students' academic achievements, counselors should focus on the final examination. It is important to pay close attention to students' reviews and examination results. Counselors should especially remind students with academic difficulties to abide by the examination discipline, avoid absenteeism, truancy, or cheating behavior, and inform them of the possible serious consequences (Li et al., 2020). To ensure a smooth start to the new semester, counselors should communicate with students' parents to identify any issues that may affect their academic performance. Meanwhile, the teaching office should use the teaching management system to review students' academic performance and issue academic warnings to those who have failed subjects. This includes scheduling make-up exams and retakes as necessary. Attention to the graduation audit is crucial to ensuring students graduate smoothly. The teaching office should review students' academic performance in advance, inform them of any graduation or degree issues, and provide remedial measures and possible consequences in a timely manner. Additionally, the teaching office should collaborate with counselors, psychologists, and parents to help students solve academic problems and avoid crises. Monitoring changes in academic status is crucial for maintaining students' academic stability. When students experience changes in academic status, such as switching majors, repeating grades, delaying graduation, or dropping out, counselors and academic offices should provide special attention and communicate promptly with classroom teachers, peer tutors, and counseling centers to ensure the students' physical and mental well-being and academic stability (Li et al., 2020).

TO STRENGTHEN THE THREE-DIMENSIONAL SUPPORT SYSTEM AND DEEPEN THE COMPREHENSIVE ACADEMIC EARLY WARNING MECHANISM

To enhance digital empowerment, establish a comprehensive academic information database, and utilize information technology and other methods to detect and identify potential and actual academic issues of students at an early stage through the collection and analysis of data on students' course management, daily attendance, school registration management, and academic completion. At the same time, schools should use advanced technologies such as big data and artificial intelligence to conduct in-depth analysis of academic data. This can help accurately identify academic risks and improve the timeliness of early warning. Establish a precise support system that follows a 'one life, one policy' approach. Improve the support system for students experiencing academic difficulties by formulating personalized support plans that accurately meet their specific needs. Keep a good record of the support process and provide timely encouragement and feedback. Additionally, establish early warning measures that are diversified and personalized based on the type and severity of academic problems. These measures may include attendance warnings, performance warnings, psychological warnings,

and more. For students who have poor attendance, an attendance warning may be implemented. For students who have failing grades or a noticeable decline in grades, an academic warning may be implemented, and counseling may be provided. For students who have psychological problems, the school should provide psychological warnings and necessary support.

CONCLUSION

An academic early warning mechanism for college students is crucial to improving the quality of talent cultivation and promoting overall student development. It is also an important tool for enhancing the education management system and teaching level. Local colleges and universities should recognize the importance of the academic early warning mechanism and implement a suitable one for their own schools, considering their own realities. This study analyzes the shortcomings of the current academic early warning mechanism in terms of flexibility, systematicity, and synergy through a literature review and descriptive research. Based on the concept of "Three All-round Education", it explores and constructs the 'synergy of the main body—cycle development—three-dimensional support' mechanism. We explored the construction of an academic early warning mechanism for college students based on the concept of "Three All-round Education" with subject synergy, cycle development, and three-dimensional support". The study found that promoting the optimal allocation of educational resources, comprehensive student development, and sustainable university development can be achieved by emphasizing the synergy of educational subjects, strengthening the construction of a three-dimensional support system based on the whole cycle of students' academic development, and realizing full participation, full-process monitoring, and all-round support.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study addresses the deficiencies of the academic early warning mechanism for college students. A new mechanism based on the concept of "Three All-round Education" has been optimized and constructed. This enriches the theory of education management and provides new theoretical perspectives and ideas for education management in universities. This study aims to assist universities in identifying and addressing issues related to student's academic performance in a timely manner. It also promotes the optimal allocation of educational resources, improves the quality and efficiency of education, and supports the comprehensive development of students and the sustainable growth of universities.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Due to time and resource constraints, this study may not be able to conduct a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of all relevant factors, which may result in some one-sidedness in the findings. Additionally, there may be variations in academic early warning mechanisms across different schools and regions, and therefore, the conclusions and recommendations of this study may not be universally applicable. Additionally, the implementation of the 'all-member + all-process + all-round' academic early warning mechanism is still in its initial stage. Without sufficient data support,

it may not be possible to fully verify and evaluate the effectiveness of the academic early warning mechanism.

FURTHER RESEARCH

The study will focus on selecting representative local applied undergraduate colleges and universities in western China as the research object. An implementation plan will be formulated, and data will be collected and analyzed through interviews, questionnaire surveys, academic performance records, student behavior data, and other methods. The aim is to assess the implementation effect of the academic early warning mechanism and provide references and information for other colleges and universities. This will push forward the application and development of academic early warning mechanisms in a wider context.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

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